

Visualization of Relative Cochlear Motions using High Resolution Optical Coherence Microscopy

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Abstract. In this study, we characterize and visualize (via motion-magnified high-resolution video) absolute and relative cochlear responses of low frequency apical regions in excised *in situ* mammalian cochleae. High-resolution motion measurements, with a subnanometer aggregate motion noise-floor, are obtained through a submillimeter optical access hole using a custom Doppler optical coherence microscopy (DOCM) system (40x water immersion objective, 0.8 numerical aperture). Results include characterizations of spatial modes of absolute and relative motion of all visible structures in radial cross-sections of the organ of Corti. Motion-magnified movie visualization shows rotation about the inner pillar, and a nearly constant phase in the sensory epithelium. The tectorial membrane leads by a fraction of a radian in phase. Responses to stapes clicks show an immediate "fast wave" response towards scala vestibuli (likely due to the optical access hole), followed by a delayed sinusoidal response with a period corresponding to CF, assumed to be a response to the induced traveling wave. This fast wave component can be temporally separated to reduce the confounding effect of the optical access hole, while simultaneously benefiting from the increased resolution it provides. To visualize relative motions, we estimate the complex displacement of chosen references and subtract that motion from all points along its transverse axis. Motions relative to the reticular lamina are small relative to absolute motions. The most significant relative motions are at the basilar membrane, which exhibits a rocking motion, however, it is difficult to dissect OHC and Deiter's Cell contributions. Motions relative to the base of hair cells are also small relative to absolute motions. The most significant relative motions are those of the TM and BM, which could be due to both Deiter Cell and OHC compression and elongation.

BACKGROUND

Recent progress in our understanding of cochlear mechanisms has been fueled in part by technical innovations that have enabled measurements of cochlear motions with unprecedented resolution. Applications of optical coherence tomography (OCT) to the study of cochlear mechanics has been especially effective – having led to direct observation and quantification of mechanisms that could not previously be experimentally tested [1-25].

We have developed a novel Doppler optical coherence microscopy (DOCM) system [1] to measure nanometer-scale motions of cochlear structures in the axial direction (parallel with the beam). DOCM combines the principles of laser Doppler vibrometry (LDV) with optical coherence tomography (OCT). As with OCT, DOCM images are constructed using optical range information, and high resolution images can be acquired using low numerical aperture access. As with LDV, DOCM uses a heterodyne method to shift information about audio frequency motion to higher frequencies, where they can be detected without contamination by low-frequency sources of noise and without the phase ambiguity. This novel combination of LDV and OCT is used to measure displacements of weakly scattering structures throughout the cochlear partition.

Cochleae used for *in vitro* studies, were excised with the stapes intact, affixed to a Petri dish, and immersed in artificial perilymph equilibrated at pH 7.3. A small ~0.5 mm apical opening was created in the temporal bone to allow for optical access through scala vestibuli. A probe placed in contact with the stapes was driven by a piezoelectric crystal to provide cochlear stimulation.

RESULTS

High resolution imaging. Using Doppler optical coherence microscopy (DOCM) described in detail in Page 2014 [1], we are able to obtain high axial and lateral resolution of the cochlear partition (Fig. 1). Structures such as the basilar membrane (BM), tunnel of Corti (ToC), inner hair cells, outer hair cells (OHCs), tectorial membrane (TM), inner sulcus, and Reissner's membrane are clearly visible.

FIGURE 1. (a) Apical cross-section (275 Hz characteristic place) of an *in vitro* Mongolian gerbil (G8208) cochlear partition

Motion measurements. Cochlear motions are nanometer in scale, compared to the micrometer scale size of the structures themselves. In addition to detailed images, DOCM provides simultaneous motion measurements at each point, with the same axial ($\sim 2.38 \mu\text{m}$) and lateral resolution ($\sim 389 \text{ nm}$). These motion measurements come through a separate directionally sensitive heterodyne channel and yield, with subnanometer accuracy, displacements and phases of structures throughout the partition. Figure 2 shows the displacement and phase maps in response to a 275 Hz ~ 75 dB SPL sinusoidal input at the stapes. Increased displacement can generally be observed moving outward radially from the modiolus, displaying a rocking pivot centered about the inner sulcus.

FIGURE 2. (a) Displacement and (b) Phase of apical cross-section (275 Hz characteristic place) of an *in vitro* Mongolian gerbil (G8208) cochlear partition in response to ~ 75 dB SPL equivalent sound pressure level stapes stimulation at 275 Hz.

Two-tone stimulus. Cochlear responses are profoundly nonlinear as illustrated by two-tone rate suppression effects such as in Fig. 3. Figure 3A shows the displacement at the same location and displacement scale as figure 2A, however the displacement has been drastically reduced due to the addition of a second tone added to the original 275 Hz tone of 343.75 Hz, or 1.25 times the original tone. This second tone induces a response basal to the measurement location and reduces the effect of the original tone at the characteristic place. The displacement and phase maps, when scaled appropriately, exhibit similar relative displacement and phase behavior as the original tone by itself. However, the phase map shows an overall larger phase delay due to the addition of the second tone.

FIGURE 3. (a) Displacement of apical cross-section (275 Hz characteristic place) of an *in vitro* Mongolian gerbil (G8208) cochlear partition in response to ~75 dB SPL equivalent sound pressure level stapes stimulation at 275 Hz + 343.75Hz at same scale as Fig. 2a. (b) Same displacement, but displacement scale is reduced to relevant range. (c) Phase in radians.

Click response. Monitoring the cochlear partition and introducing a click input to the stapes, reveals the temporal impulse response of cochlear partition. The red arrow in Fig. 4(a) denotes the location of measurement on the reticular lamina displayed in Fig. 4(b). The click response of the RL shows an early peak, attributed to the fast wave, and a later oscillation, delayed by approximately 2 ms, that corresponds to the best frequency. The later response consists of an early part in the direction of scala tympani, followed by displacement towards scala vestibuli.

Although, the presence of an optical access hole in the apical temporal bone allows for high-resolution image and motion measurements due to the unrestricted optical access, it also allows fluid to escape from scala vestibuli during the fast wave which may confound steady-state measurements. Responses from basilar membrane and tectorial membrane traveling waves can be isolated by temporally separating the fast wave responses from those that come later. Thus, we are able to obtain high resolution, precision measurements, while still being physically relevant.

FIGURE 4. Click response of an apical cross-section (275 Hz characteristic place) of an *in vitro* Mongolian gerbil (G8208) taken at (a) a point along the reticular lamina (denoted by red arrow). (b) RL displacement vs. time shows temporal response of RL.

Relative/Differential Motion/Interaction. Although much of the cochlear partition at a given location along the spiral undergoes motion due to sound-induced pressure waves traveling the length of the cochlea, we are most interested in how these structures interact relative to each other. Structures bob along these waves with different magnitudes and phases, interacting with each other in complex ways. One approach to get an overarching view of what is globally occurring, is to magnify the motions of these structures and view “in real-time,” the cross-sectional partition’s response to sound as a video. We can go further by eliminating the wave itself, and reference the motions of surrounding structures to a single structure to elucidate how that structure views those around it relatively. This approach of “real-time” visualization of global motion and relative motions referenced to various structures, can be varied with different stimuli paradigms such as pure-tone, two-tone, and click-responses.

Relative axial motion within the cochlear partition can be determined by axially “zeroing out” the complex magnitude and phase of measured absolute motion of a reference plane to points along its physiologically relevant axis (which may not be the same as the measurement axis). A white line, parallel and along the reticular lamina (Fig. 5(a)), denotes the reference plane. Figures 5(b) and (c) are the measured magnitude and phase of displacement along that plane, with a 6-point moving average shown as a solid blue line. The red line in Fig. 5(a) denotes the axis to be referenced, and is chosen in this case to be parallel to the axis of the OHCs. The complex displacement of each point along the reference plane is subtracted from that of its axial plane (parallel to the red line). Figures 5(d) and (e) show the resulting magnitude and phase of the entire cochlear partition, referenced to the plane of the reticular lamina. The magnitude and phase relationships vary greatly along different lengths of each structure, and are best visualized by applying the forementioned video algorithms [26].

FIGURE 5. (a) Differential complex axial motion, referenced to the average complex motion along the reticular lamina (white line in (a)), is determined by subtracting that motion along lines that parallel the outer pillar cells (red line). (b) Magnitude and (c) phase of reticular lamina motion along reference plane (white line from (a)). (d) Relative displacement and (e) phase of the cochlear partition, referenced to reticular lamina. (f) Moving the reference plane to below the outer hair cells yields (g) relative displacements and (h) phase of the cochlear partition, referenced to the base of the outer hair cells.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Sisto, Renata]: I was astonished by the incredible motion of the Organ of Corti you have been able to capture. I took some videos as I am really interested in this images but they are insufficient to fully understand what it is happening. I guess that the motion was captured by stimulating at high stimulus levels. Sometimes it seems as if the stimulus levels were changed during the movie but I am not sure about that. Would it be possible to share some videos with the relative explanations? I mean the stimulus levels mainly. My congratulations for all of you!

[Page, Scott]: The stimulus levels were all performed at 75 dB SPL for the above experiments. Some videos depict absolute motion of the cochlear partition, with motions up to 125 nm peak to peak. Relative motion videos may look like they have less stimulus as they are referenced to a particular absolute motion, but they are just another way to look at the same stimulus.

[Wisniowiecki, Anna]: Thank you for the interesting talk. Visualizing relative motion seems like a good approach for understanding mechanics of the organ of Corti although some experiments (such as with hearing mutations) may require knowing the absolute motion. It is hard to pick just the right reference location on OCT or the organ of Corti. Have you thought about using an optimization method to find locations that maximize and minimize the relative motion? This may help you find the pivot points in the organ of Corti – perhaps there are multiple if you search locally across the organ of Corti. One suggestion for displaying your movie data without a multimedia file, which might work for you, is to present figures showing sequences of certain timepoints with guidelines to help visualize the changing location of structures.

There are a few points which would be helpful to clarify.

- Is it correct that your OCT/OCM system is a time domain OCT system? Describing TD-OCT can be confusing for those studying hearing since most of the field uses frequency domain systems. So, it would be helpful to make this distinction. Also, reference to the Doppler effect in the OCT community is primarily used when referring to functional measurements in OCT (vibrometry or angiography).

- What is the optical resolution and wavelength of your OCT system?

- Could you explain how you stimulated the excised cochlea? Did you place a piezoelectric element at the oval window?

- Are your figures/movies describing measurements that are sensitive to motion along a single axis (the optical axis)? If you were to measure the 3D motion vector, how would you approach measuring relative motion? What relative measurements do you think would be most interesting in this case?

[Page, Scott]: Yes, this is a time domain OCT vibrometry system, which detects the Doppler shift of light from a moving target. I've updated the text to reflect this, thanks! The wavelength of the system is 841 nm with a bandwidth of 47.8 nm. With a 0.8 numerical aperture objective, the axial resolution is $\sim 2.38 \mu\text{m}$, and the lateral resolution is $\sim 389 \text{ nm}$. I've updated the text to denote these resolutions and to describe the piezoelectric stimulation of the stapes. All motions are describing axial motion (parallel to the beam) along a single axis. I think relative motion in a 3D space would be interesting when referenced from a single point. Your suggestion of minimizing and maximizing reference points is a good one. Additional details regarding the system are contained in Page 2014. Thanks!

[Fridberger, Anders]: Many thanks for a great talk and a nice paper. Those movies were captivating! The morphology of the TM in Fig 1 is very different from the guinea pig apex. Is this the way the TM usually looks at the apex of the gerbil cochlea? I also notice there does not appear to be a subtectorial space. Can it be identified if the images are zoomed up?

[Page, Scott]: Yes! The morphology of the tectorial membrane in the gerbil is very different from that of the guinea pig. To your point, the pictures we get with DOCM look very much like the morphology described by Edge et al 1998 [27], who used a traditional histological sectioning technique.

As you point out, the subtectorial space is not easily discernable in these images, however, when viewed on a linear scale the subtectorial space can be seen, however fainter parts of the image are less visible. The figure below illustrates this:

[Manley, Geoff]: I was very surprised to see the huge distance between the outer edge of the tectorial membrane and the reticular lamina. Because in earlier studies of unfixed mouse cochleae, and in other animals, there is a marginal net, which covers the outer edge of the tectorial membrane and is continuous with the surface of the organ of Corti. In other words, there is no space in those studies, which would suggest that either those studies were not correct, or that your material is not in good shape. Can you comment on that?

[Page, Scott] [updated response]: The tectorial membrane of the gerbil looks very different from other species that we've imaged with the same system. In particular, the lateral edge is much thicker and denser than that of mice and guinea pigs, as previously seen by Edge et al 1998 [27]. We've often seen increasing separation between the tectorial membrane and reticular lamina at the lateral edge with time. These images were taken about a half hour post-mortem, so we expect that some of the separation in this image probably represents some deterioration of the preparation.